

MEASURED LAMB WAVE RADIATION PATTERNS FROM [011] MN-PMN-PZT RELAXOR FERROELECTRIC DISKS ON A COMPOSITE PLATE

B. S. Vien¹, S. D. Moss², W. K. Chiu¹, C. Rosalie², N. Rajic², M. Paxevanos², and H. J. Kissick²

¹ Department of Mechanical and Aerospace Engineer, Monash University, Clayton, VIC 3800, Australia, Ben.Vien@monash.edu; Wing.Kong.Chiu@monash.edu

² Defence Science Technology Group, Fishermans Bend, VIC 3207, Australia, Scott.Moss@dst.defence.gov.au; Cedric.Rosalie@dst.defence.gov.au; Nik.Rajic@dst.defence.gov.au; Mason.Paxevanos@dst.defence.gov.au; Henry.Kissick@dst.defence.gov.au

Keywords: Relaxor Ferroelectric, Acoustic Ultrasonics, Composite Plate

ABSTRACT

Relaxor ferroelectric disk actuators of [011] poled Mn-Pb(Mg_{1/3}Nb_{2/3})O - lead zirconate titanate (Mn-PMN-PZT) single crystal and [100] poled piezoelectric PZT were bonded to 2.2 mm thick composite plate. The disk actuators were excited using a 148 V 5.5 cycle Hann-windowed voltage tone-burst at centre frequency of 200 kHz. The modal compositions of the guided plate waves generated were quantified using three-dimensional laser Doppler vibrometry. The wave mode radiation patterns are shown to be anisotropic, depending on both the crystal orientation of the actuator and the orientation of the composite fibres, suggesting that the classical theory describing guided-wave modal excitability may need to be revised for these materials.

1 INTRODUCTION

There is significant interest in using guided-wave propagation for structural health monitoring (SHM) due to their ability to provide wide and rapid coverage [1]. However, guided-waves can be highly dispersive and difficult to excite selectively, which can limit diagnostic effectiveness, especially in anisotropic materials. Composite structures exhibit higher damping than metallic structure due to the viscoelastic nature of the matrix and fibre material [1]. This damping can be dependent on: (i) fibre type and orientation [2, 3], (ii) geometry and the interaction and friction at the fibre/matrix interface [4], and (iii) imperfections in the laminate [5-7]. This damping can lead to anisotropic decay of amplitude of various guided wave modes and therefore cannot be ignored in nondestructive evaluation (NDE) and SHM applications.

Relaxor ferroelectric single crystal actuators offer the potential to improve the diagnostic effectiveness of guided plate-wave inspection. These materials have a superior piezoelectric response when compared with traditional piezoelectric PZT ceramics. For example, the power density of [011] Mn-PMN-PZT single crystals is over five times higher than that of PZT4 ceramic [8, 9]. Few studies have reported on the use of relaxor ferroelectric single crystals for structural diagnostic inspection, and the ability of [011] poled crystal disks to generate a shear horizontal wave may be useful for inspection of delamination-type defects in composite materials [1].

This study uses three-dimensional (3D) laser vibrometry to experimentally investigate the generation of fundamental Lamb and shear horizontal waves by relaxor ferroelectric single crystal transducers (poled in the [011] direction) in a quasi-isotropic composite plate. Wave amplitudes and the radiation patterns produced by the relaxor ferroelectric single crystals in a composite plate are investigated and compared to those from the piezoelectric ceramic transducer.

2 METHOD

A quasi-isotropic composite square plate with 580 mm side length and 2.2 mm thickness was

manufactured with a $[90,-45,45,0,0,45,-45,90]_s$ layout using “Cycom® 5250-4” BMI carbon fibre unidirectional pre-preg. The material properties of the lamina ply are shown in Table 1. Relaxor ferroelectric single crystals with $[011]$ poling (Ceracomp HPSC200-145, henceforth ‘HPSC’) and piezoceramic Pz26 Navy I hard piezoelectric (Meggit Ferroperm Pz26) disk elements, with a diameter of 6.35 mm and a thickness of 0.5 mm, were bonded to the composite plate using silver loaded epoxy (Circuit Works CW2400). A three-axis laser vibrometer (POLYTEC CLV 3000) was used to acquire the out-of-plane (OOP) and in-plane velocity components of the propagating Lamb waves. For improved signal-to-noise, retroreflective thin-film material (POLYTEC) was attached to the plates. Figure 1 shows the experimental arrangement.

Table 1: Material properties of Lamina ply [10] where x, y and z are fibre, transverse to the fibre and normal directions.

Lamina ply	
Elastic modulus (GPa)	
$E_{xx} = 162, E_{yy} = E_{zz} = 9.7, G_{xy} = G_{yz} = G_{xz} = 5.9$	
Poisson's ratio $\nu_{xy} = \nu_{yz} = \nu_{xz} = 0.3$	
Density $\rho = 1.5\text{g/cm}^3$	

Figure 1: Experimental arrangement showing disk actuator bonded to a composite plate, with retroreflective thin-film bonded to the plate.

The crystal orientation and the in-plane piezoelectric constants were determined using a method described in a recent paper [11]. The HPSC piezoelectric ‘1-axis’ with corresponding piezoelectric constant d_{31} was aligned along the fibre orientation angle 0-degree axis, and hence the HPSC piezoelectric ‘2-axis’ (with piezoelectric constant d_{32}) was aligned with the 90 degree outer layer fibre direction. The HPSC and Pz26 transducers were excited with 148 V peak-to-peak 5.5-cycle Hann-windowed voltage tone-bursts at centre frequency of 200 kHz, which are below the cut-off frequency for the first order Lamb waves for the composite plate and, thus, only three fundamental modes are present in the frequency range, the symmetric (S0), antisymmetric (A0) and shear horizontal (SH0). A square plate region 140 mm by 140 mm in size, centred on the transducer, was scanned at a 1 mm spatial resolution at a sample rate of 10 MHz. Synchronous averaging was applied to improve the signal noise ratio of velocity measurements.

Radiation patterns were acquired using the following approach:

- A two-dimensional (2D) fast Fourier transform (FFT) was applied to the measured wave-fields to produce a set of empirical Lamb wave dispersion curves which were then compared to the model predictions from the software package DISPERSE [12] and an analytical solution based on the material properties of the composite plate.
- Wave modes in all three Cartesian components were identified by applying this process to datasets taken along a radial line 60 mm in length and starting 10 mm from the centre of

the transducer. This was repeated for ~ 4 degree increments in the angular range of 0 to 88 degrees, with additional measurements at 2 and 90 degrees, which was sufficient due to the symmetry of the composite plate.

- Directional amplitudes corresponding to each mode were obtained directly from the empirical dispersion curves. The amplitude for each wave mode, for each angle, is then determined by taking the absolute magnitude of its directional amplitudes. Cubic spline interpolation was applied to the amplitude profiles to clarify the radiation pattern.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This section will present and discuss initial results, in particular, the velocity components of the propagating Lamb waves produced by Pz26 and HPSC actuators. Figures 2 and 3 show an example of a measured 140 by 140 mm 2D scan response at 30 μ s. The HPSC radiation profiles and amplitude of the in-plane and out-of-plane modal composition are shown to be anisotropic.

Figure 2: Measured velocity components generated by a Pz26 actuator at 200 kHz. a) Horizontal direction. b) Vertical direction. c) Out-of-plane direction.

Figure 3: Measured velocity components generated by an HPSC actuator at 200 kHz. a) Horizontal direction. b) Vertical direction. c) Out-of-plane direction.

Figure 4: Experimental dispersion curves from HPSC excitation with a centre frequency of 200 kHz. a) Horizontal direction. b) Vertical direction. c) Out-of-plane direction. Measurements are along the 90 degree (fibre direction).

Figure 4 shows 2D FFT experimental dispersion curves indicating the presence of A0, S0, and SH0 waves, obtained from velocity measurements taken in the 90 degree fibre direction along a line spanning

from 10 mm to 70 mm from the source centre over a time duration of 60 μ s. Unlike isotropic plates, a wave packet propagating in an anisotropic plate does not travel in the same direction as the phase velocity [7]. Furthermore, the phase velocity dispersion curves are angle dependent which is due to the anisotropic behavior of the composite [13]. In Figure 5 the A0 wavenumber is tracked between 0 and 90 degrees, and the results show a decrease in wavenumber by 12.2% as it approaches 90 degrees. This directionality in the A0 wavenumber is consistent with its known sensitivity to the stiffness of the outer plies in a laminate, which for the present lay-up is highest in the 90 degrees direction.[14, 15].

Figure 5: Experimental A0 wavenumber in composite plate, between 0 and 90 degrees, at 200 kHz .

The radiation patterns for the single crystal HPSC element shown in Figure 6 exhibit much stronger directionality than the corresponding patterns for the Pz26 element, which are shown in Figure 7. The patterns are evidently mode dependent, with the frequency mainly affecting the amplitude, which was experimentally observed in the isotropic plate and similar to the numerical prediction [8, 16]. In relation to the HPSC results the radiation pattern for the A0 is observed to have the highest peak at approximately 90 degrees with the smallest peak at 0 degrees. The S0 also has a maximum in the 90-degree direction, whereas the maximum for the SH0 mode is in the 45-degree direction. The amplitudes for the HPSC elements at 90 degrees are approximately 233% stronger than for Pz26 at 200 kHz. The [011] poled HPSC element generates in-plane shear deformation as a result of its large effective d_{36} coefficient, which is most likely the driving mechanisms for the observed SH0 mode [17, 18]. The excitation of A0 and S0 wave modes is primarily attributed to the dilatational deformation induced by d_{31} and d_{32} coefficients. Consequentially the superposition of the strain field due to the piezoelectric strains give rise to the directional mode patterns as shown in Figure 6. Thus, this suggests that the classical theory describing guided-wave modal excitability may need to be revised for single crystal actuators.

Figure 6: Experimental a) A0, b) SH0 and c) S0 radiation patterns in composite from 0 to 90 degrees and using HPSC disk excitation.

Figure 7: Experimental A0 and S0 radiation patterns in composite from 0 to 90 degrees and using Pz26 disk excitation.

The results in Figure 6 show that the HPSC generated A0 wave mode was dominant, especially along the fibre direction. In the HPSC, the maximum S0 and SH0 amplitudes are 45.1% and 57.3% relative to the maximum A0 amplitude. In the Pz26, the maximum S0 amplitude is 30.8% relative to the maximum A0 amplitude.

The differences in relative amplitudes compared with the previous isotropic results are attributed to: (i) the varying anisotropic decay of different guided wave modes [19, 20], and (ii) the directional orientation of the HPSC disk and the fibre orientation of the laminates [2, 3, 7, 19]. Future work

involving these new single crystal actuator materials will consider the attenuation of the guided wave modes, the effect of different d_{31} alignment and the effects of damage in a composite plate.

9 CONCLUSIONS

For the generation of acoustic waves in a composite plate, this work has demonstrated that a relaxor ferroelectric disk transducer can produce greater wave amplitudes than a traditional piezoceramic disk. A [011] poled Mn-PMN-PZT single crystal disk was shown to produce SH0 waves in a composite plate, which is not possible using conventional monolithic piezoceramic elements. The A0 wavenumber has been shown to significantly decrease in the fibre direction of the outer ply in the laminate, which is consistent with the known sensitivity of this mode to surface ply stiffness.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The financial support provided by the Australia Defence Science and Technology Group is gratefully acknowledged.

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